

MEASUREMENTS WORLD

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World in Chaos

New Approach to Understanding Quantum Gravitation

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Vasily Yanchilin, Email: yanchilin@ya.ru

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Abstract. Our space probably has an external boundary. While approaching it, the uncertainty in the motion of particles begins to increase rapidly. In this case, quantum-mechanical chaos escapes from the microcosm and fills the macroscopic world. The laws of motion degenerate and the concept of spacetime loses its physical meaning. We can find out about reality of this phenomenon by conducting high-precision measurements of the speed of light and Planck's constant.

Keywords: Centrifugal forces; absolute space; Mach's principle; measuring the speed of light; inertial reference systems; Planck's constant; macrocosm; microcosm; Chaos; gravity; experiment.

Mach's principle

Everybody knows that centrifugal forces act on the rotating carousel. However, a simple question "relative to which reference system does the carousel rotate?" still has no definitive answer.

When Isaac Newton formulated the laws of classical mechanics, he specifically postulated the existence of infinite and absolute, eternal and unchanging space to answer this question. Therefore, within Newtonian

mechanics, centrifugal forces arise when the carousel rotates relative to absolute space.

The Austrian physicist Ernst Mach did not believe in the existence of absolute space. In the late 19th century, he advanced the hypothesis that centrifugal forces arise because of the rotation of relatively fixed stars, which are remote massive objects.

Albert Einstein liked this hypothesis. He was so sure of it that he even called it a principle. Moreover, he tried

to introduce Mach's principle into his theory of gravity. Here is what he wrote about it, "...in the consistent theory of relativity, one cannot determine inertia with respect to "space", but one can determine the inertia of masses relative to each other. Therefore, if one removes any mass to a sufficiently large distance from all other masses of the Universe, the inertia of this mass should tend to zero. Let's try to formulate this condition mathematically" [1]. Nevertheless, when general relativity was constructed, it turned out that it does not satisfy Mach's principle.

What exactly causes centrifugal forces on the carousel: its rotation relative to space or its rotation relative to the stars?

The following is how Richard Feynman commented, "...we have no way, at the present time, of telling whether there would have been centrifugal force if there were no stars and nebulae around. We have not been able to do the experiment of removing all the nebulae and then measuring our rotation, so we simply do not know." [2].

Indeed, it is impossible to remove stars and galaxies, but the true cause of centrifugal forces can be learned the following way. First we must assume that Mach's principle is correct. Then we construct a theory based it. After this, we calculate the various consequences of the new theory and test them experimentally. If the experiment confirms a theory based on Mach's principle, then there is no absolute space, and centrifugal forces are caused by rotation with respect to remote massive objects. If the experiment contradicts it, then Mach's principle is not true.

Here we need to make a clarification. In this problem, the construction of a new theory is not a goal. The goal is to experimentally test Mach's principle. If we build a theory based on Mach's principle, and it turns out to be incorrect, this will also be a significant scientific result. After all, in this case we will learn Mach's principle is wrong.

So, it is a little thing: to build a theory that satisfies Mach's principle.

Inertial reference frame

What does it mean to create a theory based on Mach's principle? Let us analyze this matter. In the surrounding world, inertial reference systems play a special role, in which Newton's First law is fulfilled. In such reference systems, space and time are homogeneous and isotropic, and the light travels along a straight line. In non-inertial reference frames, the path of light is curved, and the homogeneity and isotropy of spacetime is violated. This leads to the fact that the laws of conservation of momentum and energy are not fulfilled in non-inertial reference frame.

What is the cause of the asymmetry between inertial and non-inertial reference frames?

According to Newton there is absolute space. If a reference frame moves uniformly, rectilinearly and without rotation with respect to this space, then such reference frame will be inertial.

According to Mach, an inertial reference frame has special properties because it moves uniformly and rectilinearly with respect to the stars. It turns out, if one

removes the stars, then the difference between inertial and non-inertial reference frames will disappear.

We know that in the absence of the action of forces, the body moves uniformly and rectilinearly with respect to any inertial frame of reference. According to Mach's principle, such a body moves uniformly and rectilinearly with respect to the stars. The stars with their enormous mass "hold" a body in a state of uniform and rectilinear motion. They seem to create a certain field of inertial forces. If we remove the stars one by one (take them away to infinity), then this field will gradually weaken and eventually disappear. In this case the law of inertia will not be fulfilled. Let us try to formulate this condition mathematically.

Fig. 1. In the Gravitational Ocean

Everyone knows how difficult it is to climb up. To ascend to the thirtieth floor is not the same as walking 100 meters along the road. We live in a deep potential well created by Earth's gravity. And this well is in an even deeper well created by the Sun. The Sun, in turn, is located in the galactic gravity well, and etc. How great is the well created by the entire Universe? A following comparison can help us to understand this. If the deepest cavity of the World Ocean is taken as 1 μm , then the gravitational well of Earth will be about 1 mm. And the gravity well of the Universe is 1000 km!

Figuratively speaking, we are at the bottom of the gravitational ocean of the Universe. Why do not we feel this giant pressure of gravity? We are adapted to this pressure and therefore we do not notice it. It is just like we do not notice the atmospheric pressure. If it suddenly began to fall sharply, then we would notice it. We need air pressure to live. And we also need the pressure of the Universe's gravity. If there was not this gigantic pressure,

not only we, but also mountains, rocks, our whole planet, and even the Sun would perish and collapse. The whole world would turn into Chaos.

Quantum mechanical interpretation of Mach's principle

In the early 20th century, scientists discovered that there is uncertainty in the movement of subatomic particles, because of which their behavior is fundamentally different from the behavior of classical particles. For example, an indivisible electron can pass through two closely spaced holes simultaneously. Such strange behavior of particles does not fit well with the framework of ordinary logic, but, despite this, it is well described by the laws of quantum mechanics.

In quantum mechanics, a new physical quantity, Planck's constant, is introduced. It is very small. It is due to its smallness that quantum effects are observed only in the microcosm, and macroscopic bodies obey the laws of classical mechanics. If Planck's constant suddenly began to grow, the uncertainty in the microcosm would also grow and gradually penetrate the macroscopic world. Then in the world around us, we would see the strange chaos that is observed in the microcosm.

Using quantum mechanics, we can fill Mach's principle with a fundamentally new content. Let us assume that a value of Planck's constant is determined by the fixed stars – all the masses of the Universe. It is defined as follows: if the mass of the Universe was greater, Planck's constant would be less, and vice versa. In this case, if we began to remove stars from the Universe, Planck's constant would grow tending to infinity.

Now we will not ask the question: does this assumption have a physical meaning? It is because now, first of all, we are interested in whether it satisfies Mach's principle or not.

So, as we remove the stars from the Universe, Planck's constant will increase unlimitedly. Accordingly, the uncertainty in motion of particles will increase indefinitely. Eventually, all macroscopic bodies will split into elementary particles. All clocks and rulers will split into elementary particles. In this case, the uncertainty in motion of elementary particles will tend to infinity.

Is it possible to create any *physical* reference system in such conditions? Can we somehow *measure* distances in such conditions? Can we find any periodic process, the duration of which could be taken as a unit of time? Obviously we cannot. But if we can measure neither time nor distance, does it make any sense to talk about their existence? Apparently, it does not.

If the notion of a reference frame loses its physical meaning, then, consequently, the difference between inertial and non-inertial frames of reference will lose its physical meaning, in full accordance with the requirement of Mach's principle.

It is known that Planck's constant \hbar is related to the speed of light c , the electron charge e and the fine structure constant α through the ratio:

$$c\hbar = e^2/\alpha \tag{1}$$

It is also known that in the distant past a value of the fine structure constant did not differ significantly from the current value, and, consequently, it does not depend on the distribution of matter in the Universe. Assuming that the electron charge does not depend on this distribution, we are forced to conclude:

A value of the speed of light, as well as Planck's constant, depends on the distribution of matter in the Universe. The following equality is fulfilled:

$$c\hbar = const \tag{2}$$

Using the dimensionality theorem we can obtain the following formulas for the quantities c and \hbar :

$$c^2 + \Phi = 0 \tag{3}$$

$$\hbar^2 \Phi = const \tag{4}$$

here Φ is the gravitational potential created at a given point in space by all the masses of the Universe. It is normalized so as to tend to zero in the absence of masses. With this normalization, the following inequality always is fulfilled: $\Phi < 0$.

It follows from equations (3) and (4) that in the distant past a value of the speed of light was much larger, and Planck's constant was less than at the present time.

Fig. 2. Destruction of Time

When approaching Chaos, any clock will collapse. And not only a clock. All objects of the material world including atoms will destroy.

What is primary: the laws of motion or matter? Where did the chaos in the microcosm come from?

There are two diametrically opposed viewpoints on the laws of motion.

1. The laws of motion exist independently of material bodies. If there were no large masses in the Universe and only a few test bodies existed, then these test bodies would move according to the usual laws of mechanics. Figuratively speaking, an experimenter being in a black box with his laboratory would not notice the disappearance of the rest of the Universe.

2. The laws of motion are determined by the distribution of all the matter in the Universe. If all large masses had disappeared from the Universe, then the motion of test bodies would become uncertain. This view of the laws of motion is expressed in (3) and (4). If $\Phi \rightarrow 0$, then $\hbar \rightarrow \infty$.

It can be noted that the existence of spacetime is inextricably connected with the existence of the laws of motion. It is because of the laws of motion that are universal in their nature that we can introduce different coordinate systems for describing the world and thus describe the motion of bodies within the framework of spacetime concepts.

If there were no laws of motion, then the concept of spacetime would lose its physical meaning. Spacetime would degenerate into Chaos.

From the new viewpoint, Chaos (not spacetime) is primary. Order in the Universe arises thanks to the joint efforts of all material objects. Each star contributes to the value of the gravitational potential Φ and slightly reduces a value of Planck's constant (4).

Thanks to the huge mass of the Universe, Planck's constant is so small, and Chaos manifests itself only in the microcosm. From the new viewpoint, quantum-mechanical uncertainty is the remnant of the original Chaos after imposing on it a huge gravitational field of the Universe.

The Light Formula

According to the theory of relativity, the speed of light is an absolute constant, and from the new viewpoint it depends on the gravitational potential (3). Is there any contradiction here?

The basic postulate of the theory of relativity is that the speed of light does not depend on the observer motion. You can run for a light beam or, on the contrary, run away from it. It does not matter. In any case, the light will sweep past you with the same speed 300,000 kilometers per second.

But the theory of relativity does not tell us anything about whether or not the speed of light is the same in different parts of the Universe. Therefore, equation (3) does not contradict it. Moreover, this equation explains the basic postulate of general relativity.

Indeed, the theory of relativity asserts that the speed of light does not depend on the frame of reference. In the transition from one inertial frame of reference to another one, the spacetime scale changes in such a way that a value of the speed of light remains the same. Why does the speed of light have such a privilege? Equation (3) answers this question in the following way.

A value of the speed of light is determined by the gravitational potential of the Universe. The gravitational potential is a scalar quantity characterizing a given point of space. A value of the gravitational potential does not depend on your movement. Consequently, a value of the speed of light does not depend on your movement.

Equation (3) allows us to take a fresh look at famous Einstein's formula:

$$E = mc^2 \quad (5)$$

Why does any mass have such great energy? The answer is: because it is in the huge gravitational field of the Universe. The total energy of mass m , as can be seen from equation (3), is exactly equal to its potential energy taken with the opposite sign:

$$mc^2 = -m\Phi \quad (6)$$

As a result, for any object the sum of its total and potential energy is identically zero!

$$mc^2 + m\Phi \equiv 0 \quad (7)$$

Fig. 3. The Light Formula

The speed of light has a special status in modern physics. You can move towards the light beam or, conversely, "run away" from it. In any case, the light will move past you equally fast, at 300 thousand km/s! Why does the speed of light have such a privileged position? It is because the speed of light is determined by the gravitational potential of the Universe, that is, it depends only on the distribution of all the matter in the Universe. The greater the density of stars and galaxies in the Universe the higher the speed of light in it. It follows from the light formula that at the very edge of the Universe, where its gravitational potential is almost zero ($\Phi \rightarrow 0$), the speed of light is also zero. This means that space and time on the edge of the Universe will collapse and turn into Chaos.

Let us weigh the Universe!

According to the latest astrophysical data on the study of relic radiation, the radius of the Universe is: $R \approx 78$ billion light years at its age $T \approx 13,7$ billion years. According to general relativity, such a large radius was due to the fact that the space traveled by the light in the early Universe itself increased in size. However, these data may still change, especially given the fact that the speed of light decreases with the expansion of the Universe.

It is not difficult to estimate the gravitational potential of the Universe Φ , which is of the order of magnitude

$$\Phi \approx -\frac{GM}{R} \quad (8)$$

Here M is the mass of the Universe; G is the gravitational constant. Using formula (3), we can estimate the mass of the Universe:

$$M \approx \frac{c^2 R}{G} \quad (9)$$

Substituting the numerical values we get: $M \approx 10^{54}$ kg. If we now calculate the average density of the Universe, we will get a value close to the critical one.

If the density is less than the critical value, the Universe will always expand. If the density is greater, the expansion will eventually change to compression. One of the main questions of modern astrophysics: why is the density of the Universe close to critical? It would seem that this value can be arbitrary, for example, a thousand times larger or a million times smaller. Why is such an exact hit?

In addition, it is still unknown: is our Universe open or closed? This is due to the fact that the density of the Universe is close to the critical one, and the error of measurement is quite large. There is still a hidden mass! So, we will never know: what is the future of the Universe?

From the new viewpoint, we can estimate the mass of the Universe, even without knowing anything about the large-scale distribution of galaxies! From the Light formula (3) it immediately follows that the Universe is closed. It does not matter how fast the galaxies scatter. In any case, they move slower than light, and the escape velocity of the Universe is exactly equal to the speed of light.

Here a reader may object. To determine the mass of the Universe we used formula (3). But we do not know whether it is true or not. I agree. However, in order to find out whether formula (3) is true or not, we do not need to know the mass of the Universe. We can verify the truth of this formula in terrestrial conditions measuring with high accuracy whether the speed of light depends on the gravitational potential. After doing this experiment, we will catch two birds with one stone. First, we will learn whether Mach's principle is correct or not. Secondly, if it turns out to be correct, we will be able to determine the total mass of the Universe and even claim that it is closed.

Quantum machinery of gravitational attraction

It is known that all bodies attract one another, but it is not known why this happens. Newton's law of universal gravitation (or its modification made by Einstein in general relativity) allows us to calculate how a certain body will move in a gravitational field. This law describes very well how the gravitational interaction occurs. But it does not say a word about why bodies attract each other. In other words, what physical "machinery" does gravitational attraction have?

The following is what Richard Feynman wrote about this in his lectures on physics, "What about the machinery of it? All we have done is to describe how the earth moves around the sun, but we have not said what makes it go. Newton made no hypotheses about this; he was satisfied to find what it did without getting into the

machinery of it. No one has since given any machinery." [2].

Within the framework of the new model, we can give a simple and obvious explanation to the machinery of gravitational interaction. Consider a particle localized in a neighborhood of point A . Since there is a quantum uncertainty in its motion, then there is a probability that after some time it will be in the neighborhood of point B . There is also the probability of an inverse transition. In an empty space, these probabilities are equal. But if point B is closer to a massive object than point A (Fig. 4), then an uncertainty in the particle motion in it will be less.

Fig. 4. The Machinery of Gravitational Attraction

Consequently, the probability of the particle passing from a neighborhood of point A to a neighborhood of point B is greater than the probability of an inverse transition.

From the new viewpoint, the gravitational interaction can be considered as a quantum effect. Near a large mass, the uncertainty in the particle motion decreases, as a result of which it moves toward a large mass.

The proposed machinery of gravitational interaction not only allows explaining why all bodies attract one another. It also explains why the gravitational interaction is so weak. This is a consequence of the fact that the uncertainty in motion is limited mainly by the remote masses of the Universe. Closely located bodies reduce the uncertainty by a very small percentage.

Chaos and Space

The basic physical idea underlying the new approach to Mach's principle is the idea of existence of Chaos outside the gravitational field of the Universe. From the new viewpoint, time and space, in which we live, exist only within the Universe and only thanks to the vast masses that fill the Universe. Our Universe is an island surrounded by Chaos [3, p.245].

We are accustomed to space and time and perceive them as the foundation of our world, existing independently of material bodies. From the new point of view, this is not correct. If there were no huge masses in the Universe, then space and time would collapse into Chaos. It is difficult to imagine Chaos, but still possible. This is the uncertainty observed in the microcosm, which is increased to the size of the Universe.

From the new viewpoint, the Cosmos is an equilibrium and harmony between the uncertainty (which is the result of the influence of Chaos) and Order that arises from the gravitational interaction that pervades the entire Universe.

In order to verify the existence of Chaos it is necessary to carry out experiments to verify equations (3) and (4). It follows from these equations that values of

the speed of light and Planck's constant should vary with the height above the Earth surface. As can be easily estimated, the relative change in these values is approximately 10^{-16} per meter of climb, which corresponds to the capability of modern technology. This means that a new model of spacetime can be tested experimentally in the near future.

By the way, if Planck's constant does decrease near a large mass (4), then a rate of an atomic clock should increase near the Earth surface in defiance of general relativity. The experiment with atomic clocks in the gravitational field of Earth is described in detail in the article "Atomic Physics vs. General Relativity" (*Measurements World*, 2010, No.12).

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